

Towards Improved Findability of Energy Research Software by Introducing a Metadata-based Registry

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Agenda

- Motivation
- Vision
- Related Work
- Approach
- Summary and Outlook

Motivation: Research in the Energy Domain

- Key challenges:
 - Energy transition
 - Safety-critical infrastructure
 - Interdisciplinary environment
 - Cyber-physical energy systems
- Most research is based on simulations:
 - Behavior of components (PV, batteries, ...)
 - Control strategies for energy systems
 - Grid planning
 - Transition of the energy system

› Energy Research Software (ERS) is fundamental for Energy Research

Motivation: Challenges for Energy Research Software

- Increasing complexity
- Provided code hardly findable
- Software rarely reused

→ Multiple frameworks with overlapping features

→ A lot of time spent to develop code which already exist somewhere

→ Code is often only use once

→ High development costs

› Energy Research Software needs to become more findable to be reused

Motivation: Findable Energy Research Software

- From the FAIR criteria [1]:
 - Findability can be improved through
 - good general metadata
 - registration of a software with metadata in a registry
 - Accessibility and Interoperability can be improved through
 - good metadata as context
 - Reuse can be simplified
 - metadata including conditions for reuse as license and how to cite

➤ **Metadata and a Metadata Registry can make Energy Research Software more Findable**

Vision

Metadata-based Registry for Energy Research Software

Metadata-based Registry for Energy Research Software

Metadata-based Registry for Energy Research Software

Requirements 1/2

- Useable for all types of energy research software
 - From long-term to short-term
- Application profile for energy research software
 - Reuses elements from existing metadata schemas
 - Improves FAIRness (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable)
 - Follows best practice in metadata schema creation
 - Uses ontologies as value vocabularies
 - Compatible with existing metadata, e.g., PyPI

Requirements 2/2

- Registry
 - Repository for metadata
 - Includes good search functionality
 - Supports all features of the application profile
 - Gives information on link-ability of software based on their metadata
- Metadata Generation Tool
 - Usable for all researchers in the energy domain without further knowledge
 - Automatically collects metadata from GitHub, GitLab, Google Scholar
 - Supports the use of value vocabularies (existing ontologies)

Related Work

Overview

Scope					
CodeMeta	General Research Software	✗	✓	✗	~
OntoSoft	Research Software in GeoScience	✗	✓	✓	~
Bio.Tools	Research Software in LifeScience	✗	~	✓	~
EngMeta	Research Data in Engineering	~	✓	~	✓
Open Energy Platform	Research Software in Energy Research	✓	~	✓	~

Open Energy Platform

- Framework Factsheet
 - Not a formalized schema
 - Not based on existing schemas
 - Does not yet support the use of a value vocabulary
- Open Energy Ontology [10]
 - Domain Ontology for the energy domain
 - Can be used for annotating data & software

Framework Factsheet: Mosaik

Overview

Last updated ?	2021-05-08
Open Source ?	✓
License ?	GNU Lesser General Public License v3.0

General Information

Mathematical Description

Openness

Model Building

References

Own Approach

Approach Step 1: Development of Domain Model (like proposed by [11]) Based on a Requirement Analysis

Approach Step 2: Formalization of a Metadata Schema for ERS

Approach Step 3: Development of a Registry for ERS

- Repository for metadata
- Use of the metadata schema
- Based on existing framework like ckan (similar to TIBs Leibniz Data Manager)
- Easy usable artifact overview pages like on bio.tools
- Development of search technology based on semantic web technologies

Approach Step 4: Building a Metadata Generation Tool for ERS

- Tool supporting researchers in generating metadata
- Support for the use of value vocabulary
- Automatically extracts metadata from GitHub, GitLab and Readme files

Summary and Outlook

- What is needed to set up a metadata-based registry which can improve the Findability of Energy Research Software?
- Approach

• Domain Model based on a Requirement Analysis

• Metadata Schema for ERS

• Registry for ERS

• Metadata Generation Tool for ERS

Appendix: Literature 1/2

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Appendix: Literature 2/2

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